

Analytical Method Development And Validation For The Estimation Of Brivaracetam By Rp-Hplc Method

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ABSTRACT

Several spectrophotometric and HPLC methods have been reported for determination in drugs and in pharmaceutical dosage forms. Hence, in the present study, a new, sensitive, suitable and robust reversed-phase high performance liquid chromatography method was developed and validated for the determination of in bulk drug and in tablet formulation. In RP-HPLC method, Methanol and Water (75:25 % v/v) was used as mobile phase, at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min, on HPLC system containing UV- detector with Openlab EZchrome software and Kromasil C18, 250 mm X 4.6 mm, 5 µm. The detection was carried out at 258 nm. The method gave suitable retention time i.e. 3.60 min for. The results of analysis in the method were validated in terms of Filter study, Solution stability, specificity, Linearity, accuracy, precision (Repeatability and intermediate precision), limit of detection, limit of quantification and robustness. A simple and precise method was developed for the assay of brivaracetam in bulk drug and in tablet formulation. The method need regular reagents for doing analysis and also less time consuming, it can be performed routinely in industry for routine analysis of bulk drug and marketed product of brivaracetam.

Keywords: RP-HPLC, Methanol, Validation., brivaracetam.

INTRODUCTION

In pharmaceutical industries, the validation of analytical method is used to demonstrate that the method is fitted for its purpose; it must follow a plan which includes scopes, Performance characteristics, and acceptance limits. Analytical methods need to be validated or revalidated prior to their introduction into routine analyses. Chromatography is an analytical techniques based on the separation of molecules due to differences in their structure and/or composition. In general, Chromatography involves moving a sample through the system over a stationary phase. The molecules in the samples will have different affinities and interaction with the stationary support, leading to separation of Molecules. Samples components that display stronger interaction with the stationary phase

will move more slowly through the column than components with weaker interaction. Different compounds can be separated from each other as they move through the column. Chromatographic separation can be carried out using a variety of stationary phases. High-Performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is types of liquid Chromatography used to separate and quantify compounds that have been dissolved in Solution. HPLC can be used to determine the amount of a specific compound in a solution.

These different dosages analyzed by different method including crystal structure elution, polarimetry, UV, IR, HPLC, LCMS, and such more technique are useful in different types of analysis in different dosage form. But now a day most important and better

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techniques in HPLC and GC by using HPLC simple reverse phase Chromatographic method develop for the determination of active content and relative impurities, while it is better to find stability indicating method for analysis. Because after some time impurities present in the product increase more than its limits and if impurities elute very close to the main drug the possibility of merging impurities in to main drug in cresses and it result in to the failure of method.[1]

1.1 Chromatography

The analytical technique of high performance liquid chromatography is used extensively throughout the pharmaceutical industry. it is used to provide information on the composition of drug related samples. The information obtained may be qualitative, indicating what compound present in the sample or quantitative are providing the actual amounts of compound in the sample. HPLC is used routinely during drug manufacture. The aim of the analysis will depend on both the nature of the sample and stage of development HPLC is a chromatographic technique:therefore, it is necessary to have basic understanding of chromatography to understand how it work. Chromatography is at technique which separates components in a mixture due to the differing time for each component to travel through stationary phase when carried through it by mobile phase. The stationary phase is fixed in place either in column (a hollow tube made up out of a suitable material e.g. Glass) or on a planner surface and the mobile phase moves over or through the stationary phase carrying with it the sample of interest. In practice the stationary

phase can be a solid, a liquid adsorbed on a solid or an organic species bonded to a solid surface. In gas chromatography and supercritical fluid chromatography the stationary phase may be fixed in place either in a column or on a planner surface. In HPLC a column is used. The Name given to liquid chromatography on a planner surface is thin layer chromatography (TLC)[2]

I) Stationary phase

It is the combination of a suitable stationary phase and mobile phase that enables the separation of a mixture and thus the analysis of the components in the mixture[3]

a) Normal phase

In mixture of components to be separated those analysts which are relatively more polar will be retained by the polar stationary phase longer than those analysts which are relatively less polar. Therefore, a least polar component will eluate first. The attractive forces which exist are mostly dipole-dipole and hydrogen bonding (polar) Interaction[4]

b) Reversed phase

In mixture of component to be separated those analysts which are less polar will be retained by the nonpolar stationary phase longer than those analyte which are relatively more polar. Therefore, the most polar components will elute first. The attractive forces which exist are mainly non-specific hydrophobic interaction. The exact nature of these interactions is still under discussion [5]

Table No.: 1 Parameter used to describe a HPLC column

Parameter	Description
Packing/Matrix	The finely divided material with which the column is packed, usually silica. It can be used as the stationary phase in the adsorption chromatography or a bonded phase is attached for use in partition chromatography.
Bonded phase	The stationary phase is chemically bonded to the packing/ matrix.
Particle size	The size of particles in column (if applicable), usually measured in microns.
Pore size	The size of the pores in the particles/ monolith, usually measured in Angstroms.
Length	The length of column, usually measured in mm.
Diameter	The internal diameter of column, usually measured in mm.
Hardware	The material used to construct the external tubing and fitting of the column.

II) Mobile phase

The mobile phase for HPLC is the liquid phase which is continually flowing through stationary phase and both the stationary phase and the nature of the compounds being Analyzed. Different properties of solvents define whether they are suitable for use as a mobile phase either under reversed phase or normal phase condition [6]

a) Solvents

The most common solvents used for HPLC are listed below in order of increasing polarity.

Water,
Methanol,
Acetonitrile,
Iso- propanol,
Tetra hydro furan,
Chloroform,
Methylene chloride,
N-Hexane

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

7.1. PRELIMINARY CHARACTERIZATION OF DRUG

7.1.1 Color, odour and appearance

Brivaracetam was evaluated for parameters like color, odour & appearance are shown in result.

7.1.2. Determination of solubility

The solubility was determined in Water at a concentration of 3 mg/mL as follows and is given in results.

Water: Weighed approx 30 mg of Brivaracetam and sonicated for 5-10 minutes to dissolve in 10 ml of Water.

7.2 Selection of analytical wavelength

7.2.1. Selection of solvent

Water was selected as the solvent for dissolving Brivaracetam.

7.2.2. Preparation of standard solutions for UV scan to determine Absorption maxima wavelength

In order to prepare stock solution, weighed accurately 10 mg Brivaracetam and transferred into 20 ml volumetric flask, added 15 ml of water and sonicated to dissolve the standard completely and diluted up to the mark with water (500 PPM). Further diluted 1.0 mL to 25 mL with water. (20 PPM)

7.2.3. Selection of analytical wavelength

Water as a blank and Brivaracetam standard solution (20 PPM) was scanned from 400 nm to 200 nm. Absorption maxima was determined for drug. Brivaracetam showed maximum absorbance at 210 nm shown in results.[7,8]

7.3 Method Development by RP – HPLC

7.3.1. Preparation of standard solution for Chromatographic development:

Brivaracetam Standard stock solution was prepared by transferring 10 mg Brivaracetam into a 20 mL clean and dried volumetric flask added about 15 mL of water to dissolve it completely and made volume up to the mark with water. (500 PPM) Further diluted 2 ml of stock solution to 10 mL with mobile phase of each trial. (100 PPM).

Selection of analytical wavelength for HPLC method development: Analytical wavelength for the examination was selected from the wavelength of maximum absorption from the spectrophotometric analysis and it was 210 nm.

7.3.2 Development of HPLC chromatographic method

Developed a method until we get good chromatography

An acceptance criterion for good chromatography is as follows:

Retention time: Optimum R.T.

Asymmetry (Tailing factor): 0.8 to 2.0

Theoretical plates: NLT 2000

Following trials are taken for estimation of Brivaracetam.

Principle: Reversed Phase Liquid Chromatography with Isocratic elution and UV detection.

Trial 1:

Chromatographic Conditions:

Standard solution: Brivaracetam 100 PPM
 Detector: U.V. Detector
 Column: Phenomenex C18,
 Column Dimension: (250 mm X 4.6 mm i.d.) 5µm
 Column Oven temperature: 35°C
 Injection Volume: 20 µl
 Wavelength: 210 nm
 Mobile phase: Methanol : Water (70:30)
 Flow Rate: 1.0 ml/min

Observation: The trial 1 results are shown in results.[9]

Trial 2:

Chromatographic Conditions:

Standard solution: Brivaracetam 100 PPM
 Detector: U.V. Detector
 Column: Phenomenex C18,
 Column Dimension: (250 mm X 4.6 mm i.d.) 5µm
 Column Oven temperature: 35°C
 Injection Volume: 20 µl
 Wavelength: 210 nm
 Mobile phase: Methanol : Water (50:50)
 Flow Rate: 1.0 ml/min

Observation: The trial 2 results are shown in results.

Trial 3:

Chromatographic Conditions:

Standard solution: Brivaracetam 100 PPM
 Detector: U.V. Detector
 Column: Phenomenex C18,
 Column Dimension: (250 mm X 4.6 mm i.d.) 5µm
 Column Oven temperature: 35°C
 Injection Volume: 20 µl
 Wavelength: 210 nm
 Mobile phase: Acetonitrile : Water (70:30)
 Flow Rate: 1.0 ml/min

Observation: The trial 3 results are shown in results.[10]

Trial 4:

Chromatographic Conditions:

Standard solution: Brivaracetam 100 PPM
 Detector: U.V. Detector
 Column: Phenomenex C18,
 Column Dimension: (250 mm X 4.6 mm i.d.) 5µm
 Column Oven temperature: 35°C
 Injection Volume: 20 µl
 Wavelength: 210 nm
 Mobile phase: Methanol : 0.05% TFAA in Water (70:30)
 Flow Rate: 1.0 ml/min

Observation: The trial 4 results are shown in results.

Trial 5:

Chromatographic Conditions:

Standard solution: Brivaracetam 100 PPM
 Detector: U.V. Detector
 Column: Phenomenex C18,
 Column Dimension: (250 mm X 4.6 mm i.d.) 5µm
 Column Oven temperature: 35°C
 Injection Volume: 20 µl
 Wavelength: 210 nm
 Mobile phase: Methanol : 0.05% TFAA in Water (60:40)
 Flow Rate: 1.0 ml/min

Observation: The trial 5 results are shown in results.

Chromatographic condition in Trial no. 5 considered as optimized method which is as follows

Chromatographic Conditions:

Detector: U.V. Detector
 Column: Phenomenex C18,
 Column Dimension: (250 mm X 4.6 mm i.d.) 5µm
 Column Oven temperature: 35°C
 Injection Volume: 20 µl
 Wavelength: 210 nm
 Mobile phase: Methanol : 0.05% TFAA in Water (60:40)
 Flow Rate: 1.0 ml/min
 Run Time: 7 min.[11]

7.4.2. Preparation of System suitability test (Brivaracetam standard solution):

Weighed about 25 mg of Brivaracetam and transferred in 50 mL volumetric flask, added 35 mL

of water, sonicated to dissolve it, made volume up to the mark with water. Pipette out 1.0 ml from standard stock solution and transferred into 25 ml volumetric flask and made volume up to the mark with mobile phase (**20 µ/mL working concentration**), chromatograms were recorded.

System suitability is a Pharmacopoeial requirement and is used to verify, whether the chromatographic system is adequate for analysis to be done. The tests were performed by collecting data from Five replicate injection of standard drug solution and the results are recorded.

Acceptance criteria

1. RSD should not be more than 2.0 % for five replicate injections of standard.
2. USP Tailing Factor/ Asymmetry Factor is not more than 2.0.
3. The column efficiency as determined for Plate Count should be more than 2000.

7.4.3. Analysis of marketed Test sample:

Marketed test sample having brand name Brivgard 50 mg tablets were selected for analysis and for doing validation.

Average weight of test sample (Brivgard 50 mg):

Weighed the 20 tablets at a time and calculated average weight of tablet by following formula:

$$\text{Average weight (mg)} = \text{Weight of 20 tablets (mg)} / 20$$

Sample preparation of Marketed test sample:

Weighed 20 tablets transferred in mortar pestle and crushed to fine powder. Mixed the contents with butter paper uniformly. Weighed the powder material equivalent to 25 mg of Brivaracetam (132.2 mg powder material) and transferred to clean and dried 50 mL of volumetric flask. Added 35 mL of water, sonicated for 15 minutes with intermittent shaking. After 15 minutes allow to cool the solution to room temperature and made volume up to the mark with water. Filtered the solution through suitable 0.45 µ syringe filter discarding 3-5 mL of initial filtrate. Further diluted 1.0 ml of filtered stock solution to 25 ml with mobile phase. (20 mcg of Brivaracetam), injected the resultant solution and chromatograms were recorded and results are recorded.[12]

Sample Prepared in duplicate. Summary of sample preparation as follows:

Sample	Sample (mg)	Diluted to (mL)	Volume taken	Diluted to (mL)
Sample 1	132.7	50	1	25
Sample 2	132.3	50	1	25

Formula for % Assay calculation:

$$\% \text{ Assay} = \frac{\text{Brivaracetam Spl area}}{\text{Brivaracetam Std avg area}} \times \frac{\text{Brivaracetam STD wt (mg)}}{50} \times \frac{1.0}{25} \times \frac{50}{\text{Tablet sample weight (mg)}} \times \frac{25}{1.0} \times \frac{\text{Avg wt of sample (mg)}}{\text{Label claim of Brivaracetam}} \times 100$$

7.5. VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD

The developed method for estimation of Brivaracetam was validated as per ICH guidelines for following parameters.

1) FILTRATION STUDY:

Filtration study of an analytical procedure checks the interference of extraneous components from filter,

deposition on filter bed and compatibility of filter with sample. This study was conducted with Brivaracetam Test sample (Tablet solution).

Filtration study carried out with unfiltered and filtered test solution. During filtration activity 0.45 µm PVDF and 0.45 µm Nylon syringe filters used by discarding 5 mL of aliquot sample.

2) STABILITY OF ANALYTICAL SOLUTION

Stability study was conducted for standard and test sample solution. Stability study was performed at normal laboratory conditions.

The solution was stored at normal illuminated laboratory conditions and analyzed after 12 hours and 24 hours.

Standard and Test solution stability study was performed by calculating the difference between results of test solution at each stability time point to that of initial.

3) SPECIFICITY:

Specificity is the ability to access unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present.

Following solution shall be prepared and injected to prove the specificity nature of the method.

I. Blank (Mobile phase as Blank)

II. Placebo

Analyzing marketed test sample contains excipients (additives) which are totally unknown. So Placebo prepared at lab level by using formula as follows:

Placebo preparation:

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Role	Qty (mg)
1	Lactose	Filler	80
2	Starch	Binder	5
3	Magnesium stearate	Lubricant	5
4	Talc	Glidant	5
5	crospovidone	Disintegrants	5
Total			100 mg

Total 10 gm of placebo prepared:

Placebo solution preparation:

Weighed 107.2 mg of placebo material (Which is equivalent to 25 mg of Brivaracetam) and transferred to clean and dried 50 mL of volumetric flask. Added 35 mL of water, sonicated for 15 minutes with intermittent shaking. After 15 minutes allow to cool the solution to room temperature and made volume up to the mark with water. Filtered the solution through suitable 0.45 μ Nylon syringe filter discarding 3-5 mL of initial filtrate. Further diluted 1.0 ml of filtered stock solution to 25 ml with mobile phase, injected the resultant solution and chromatograms were recorded.

4) LINEARITY AND RANGE

Sr. No.	Level (%)	mL of stock solution	Diluted to with Mobile phase (mL)	Brivaracetam Concentration (μ g/mL)
1	50	2.00	20	10.00
2	75	3.00	20	15.00
3	100	4.00	20	20.00
4	125	5.00	20	25.00
5	150	6.00	20	30.00

Preparation of linearity solution

The linearity of an analytical procedure is its ability (within a given range) to obtain test results which are directly proportional to the concentration (amount) of analyte in the sample.

5 levels of Linearity was performed from 10% to 150% of working concentration

Linearity Brivaracetam stock solution:

Weighed 20 mg of Brivaracetam and dissolved in 20 mL with water. Further diluted 5.0 ml of stock solution to 50 mL with water (100 μ g/mL).

Linearity levels prepared as follows:

Determination

Each level injected in triplicate and mean area calculated. Calibration curve was plotted graphically as a function of analyte concentration in $\mu\text{g/mL}$ on X-axis Vs mean area on y-axis as given in results.

Acceptance criteria

Correlation Coefficient: NLT 0.98

Intercept: To be report

Slope: To be report

5) Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ):**Detection limit:**

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value.

Quantitation limit:

The quantitation limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy.

As per ICH Q2R1 guidelines LOD and LOQ was determined by using the approach Based on the

Calibration Curve in which residual standard deviation of a regression line was calculated and determined the LOD and LOQ by using following formula:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \sigma / S$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma / S$$

Where,

σ = residual standard deviation of a regression line

S = Slope of regression line

6) ACCURACY (% RECOVERY)

The accuracy of the analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between the value which is accepted either as a conventional true value or an accepted reference value and the value of the value found,

Accuracy will be conducted in the range from 50 % to 150 % of working concentration. Solution of each accuracy level was prepared in triplicate. Calculated % Recovery for each sample, Mean % recovery for each level and overall recovery and also calculated % RSD for each level and % RSD for overall recovery.

Accuracy levels details:

Refer Following table for each sample:

Level (%)	API (mg)	Placebo	Diluted to (mL)	Volume taken (mL)	Diluted to (mL)	Conc ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
50	12.7	107.6	50	1	25	10.16
	12.5	107.1	50	1	25	10.00
	12.6	107.8	50	1	25	10.08
100	25.1	106.9	50	1	25	20.08
	25.3	107.5	50	1	25	20.24
	25.2	107.9	50	1	25	20.16
150	37.6	106.8	50	1	25	30.08
	37.5	107.2	50	1	25	30.00
	37.6	107.3	50	1	25	30.08

Procedure for preparation of Accuracy sample solution:

Take clean and dried 9 volumetric flasks of 50 mL. Weighed approx 107.2 mg of placebo and transferred

in each 50 mL volumetric flask. Weighed Brivaracetam API as per accuracy level and transferred in same 50 ml volumetric flask. Added 35 ml of water sonicated it for 15 minutes with intermittent shaking. Allowed to cool the solution at

room temperature and made the volume up to the mark with water. Filtered the solution through suitable 0.45 μ Nylon filter discarding 5 mL of filtrate. Further diluted 1.0 ml of filtrate to 25 ml with mobile phase.

Acceptance criteria

1. % Recovery for each sample and Mean recovery and overall recovery should be in the range of 98-102%.
2. The Relative Standard Deviation should not be more than 2.0%.

7) PRECISION

Precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous test under the prescribed conditions. Precision is of two types, Repeatability and Intermediate precision. It is performed on tablet test sample.

I. Repeatability:

Sample	Powder wt (mg)	Diluted to (mL)	Volume taken (mL)	Diluted to (mL)
Sample 1	132.6	50	1	25
Sample 2	133.2	50	1	25
Sample 3	132.2	50	1	25
Sample 4	132.8	50	1	25
Sample 5	132.6	50	1	25
Sample 6	132.1	50	1	25

Acceptance criteria:

% Assay: 90-110% for each sample and mean assay value

% RSD for % assay value of 6 samples: NMT 2%

Preparation of sample solution (6 Samples prepared):

Weighed 20 tablets and calculated average weight and transferred in mortar pestle and crushed to fine powder. Mixed the contents with butter paper uniformly. Weighed the powder material equivalent to 25 mg of Brivaracetam (132.2 mg powder material) and transferred to clean and dried 50 mL of volumetric flask. Added 35 mL of water, sonicated for 15 minutes with intermittent shaking. After 15 minutes allow to cool the solution to room temperature and made volume up to the mark with water. Filtered the solution through suitable 0.45 μ Nylon syringe filter discarding 3-5 mL of initial filtrate. Further dilute 1.0 ml of filtered stock solution to 25 ml with mobile phase. (20 mcg of Brivaracetam), injected the resultant solution and chromatograms were recorded.

Six samples prepared.

Precision (Repeatability) Sample details are as follows:

II. Intermediate precision

It is performed by doing analysis on another day to check reproducibility of results. Samples prepared in same manner as that of Repeatability parameter (6 Samples prepared).

Intermediate Precision Sample details are as follows:

Sample	Powder wt. (mg)	Diluted to (mL)	Volume taken (mL)	Diluted to (mL)
Sample 1	132.6	50	1	25
Sample 2	132.7	50	1	25
Sample 3	132.9	50	1	25

Sample 4	133.2	50	1	25
Sample 5	132.4	50	1	25
Sample 6	132.7	50	1	25

Acceptance criteria:

% Assay: 90-110% for each sample and mean assay value

% RSD for % assay of 6 samples of Intermediate precision: NMT 2

% RSD for Total 12 samples: NMT 2% for test results (6 of Repeatability and 6 of Intermediate precision)

8) ROBUSTNESS

The robustness of an analytical procedure is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small, but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage.

Determination: Standard solution was injected under different chromatographic conditions as shown below.

8.1.3. Solubility study**Solubility study of Brivaracetam**

Sr. No.	Name of Solvent	Observation	Conclusion	Summary
1	Water	No Drug Particles seen after sonication	Drug was found soluble in water.	Water used as a diluents for preparing stock solution.

8.2.1. Selection of solvent

Water was selected as the solvent for dissolving Brivaracetam.

a). Changes in flow rate by $\pm 10\%$. ($\pm 0.1\text{ml/min}$)

b). Change in column oven temperature. ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$)

c) Change in wavelength ($\pm 3\text{ nm}$)

8. RESULT AND DISCUSSION**8.1. PRELIMINARY CHARACTERIZATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF DRUG****8.1.1. Color, odour and appearance****Color, odour and appearance of Drug**

Sr. No	Name	Colour, odour and appearance of drug
1	Brivaracetam	White, odourless and slightly amorphous powder

8.2.3. Selection of analytical wavelength**1) Blank Water:**

Fig. No. 1 UV spectrum of Water as a blank

2) Brivaracetam STD solution: (20 PPM)

Fig. No. 2 UV spectrum of Brivaracetam

Observation: The standard solution was scanned from 400 nm to 200 nm. Wavelength of maximum absorption was determined for drug. Brivaracetam showed maximum absorbance at 210 nm. Below 210 nm wavelength cannot be select because of cut off wavelength region of many solvents. Therefore 210

nm considered as an analytical wavelength for further determination.

8.3 Method Development by RP – HPLC

8.3.1 Optimization of HPLC method

Trial 1:

Chromatogram:

Fig. No. 3 Typical chromatogram of Trial 1

Observation: Brivaracetam eluted but Trial 2:
chromatography not Acceptable.

Chromatogram:

Conclusion: Method Rejected.

Fig. No. 4 Typical chromatogram of Trial 2

Observation: Brivaracetam eluted with Trial 3:
Unacceptable chromatography. Broad peak
Observed.

Chromatogram:

Conclusion: Method Rejected.

Fig. No. 5 Typical chromatogram of Trial 3

Observation: Brivaracetam eluted with Conclusion: Method Rejected.
Unacceptable chromatography.

Trial 4:

Chromatogram:

Fig. No. 6 Typical chromatogram of Trial 4

Observation: Brivaracetam eluted but Conclusion: Method Rejected.
Chromatography not Acceptable. Splitted peak
observed.

Trial 5:**Chromatogram:****Fig. No. 7 Typical chromatogram of Trial 5**

Observation: Brivaracetam eluted at R.T. 3.14 min, with good chromatography. (Asymmetry: 1.37 & Theoretical Plate: 9126)

Conclusion: Method Accepted.

Conclusion: From the observations of trials first to five, it was concluded that chromatographic conditions in trial five gives better peak, good retention time and tailing factor therefore chromatographic conditions in trial five was subjected for validation.

Optimized Chromatographic Condition

Parameter	Description
Mode	Isocratic
Column Name	Phenomenox C18, 250 mm X 4.6mm ID, 5 µm
Detector	UV Detector
Injection Volume	20 µl
Wavelength	210 nm
Column Oven temp	35°C
Mobile Phase	Methanol : 0.05% TFAA in Water (60:40%V/V)
Flow Rate	1.0 ml/min
Run time	7 minutes

8.4. System suitability test**Results for System Suitability Test of Brivaracetam:**

Sr No.	Standard solution	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates
1	Standard_1	7451306	1.35	8849
2	Standard_2	7420154	1.34	8834
3	Standard_3	7466911	1.35	8826
4	Standard_4	7470060	1.35	8857
5	Standard_5	7452794	1.34	8842
Mean		7452245	1.35	8842
STD Dev		19770.440		
% RSD		0.27		

System Suitability Acceptance Criteria:

1. Relative standard deviation of the area of analyte peaks in standard chromatograms should not be more than 2.0 %.
2. Theoretical plates of analyte peak in standard chromatograms should not be less than 2000.
3. Tailing Factor (Asymmetry) of analyte peaks in Standard Chromatograms should be less than 2.0

Data interpretation: It was observed from the data tabulated above; the method complies with system suitability parameters. Hence, it can be concluded that the chromatographic method is adequate for intended analysis.

Fig. No. 8 Typical chromatogram Standard solution 1 of system suitability solution.

8.4.1 Analysis of Marketed Test samples (Assay)

Sample	Area	% Assay	Mean Assay
Sample 1	7490251	100.13	99.28
Sample 2	7341256	98.44	

Brivgard 50 mg Tablet:

Average weight of tablet = $5.2880 / 20 = 0.2644$ gm = 264.4 mg

Weight of 20 tablets = 5.2880 gm

Assay results of Brivgard 50 mg Tablet:

Fig. No. 9 Typical chromatogram Brivgard 50 mg Tablet sample.

Acceptance criteria:

1) % Assay found should be in the range of 90-110%.

Data interpretation:

From the above results, it can be concluded that the assay result is within the limit for selected marketed test sample and sample can be used for validation.

Results of Filter study

Sample description	Area	% Absolute difference
Unfiltered	7466025	NA
0.45 μ PVDF filter	7416397	0.66
0.45 μ Nylon filter	7432055	0.45

8.5 VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD**1) FILTRATION STUDY:**

Filtration study of an analytical procedure checks the interference of extraneous components from filter, deposition on filter bed and compatibility of filter with sample. Performed on tablet test sample.

Chromatograms:

Fig. No. 10 Typical chromatogram of unfiltered sample.

Fig. No. 11 Typical chromatogram of sample filtered through 0.45 μ PVDF filter.

Fig. No. 12 Typical chromatogram of sample filtered through 0.45µ Nylon filter.

Acceptance criteria: % Absolute difference of filtered samples NMT 2.0 w.r.t. Unfiltered sample.

Data interpretation: Both filters PVDF and Nylon passes the criteria for filter study, hence both filters can be used. We used Nylon filter because it showed less absolute difference as compare to PVDF filter.

2) SOLUTION STABILITY: Stability study was conducted for Standard as well as Test Sample. Stability study was performed at normal laboratory conditions. The solution was stored at normal illuminated laboratory conditions and analyzed at initial, after 12 hours and 24 hours.

Results of Solution stability.

Sample solution			Standard solution		
Time point	Area	% Absolute difference	Time point	Area	% Absolute difference
Initial	7435962	NA	Initial	7446020	NA
12 Hours	7390251	0.61	12 Hours	7406253	0.53
24 Hours	7369947	0.89	24 Hours	7389236	0.76

Chromatograms:

Fig. No. 13 Typical chromatogram of Standard solution Initial.

Fig. No. 14 Typical chromatogram of Standard solution After 24 Hrs.

Fig. No. 15 Typical chromatogram of Test solution Initial.

Fig. No. 16 Typical chromatogram of Test solution After 24 Hrs.

Acceptance criteria: % Absolute difference of Stability solution: NMT 2.0 w.r.t. Initial solution.

Data interpretation: Standard and Test solution was found stable up to 24 Hrs. Hence both solutions can be used up to 24 Hrs.

3) SPECIFICITY: Specificity is the ability to access unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present.

Blank & Placebo solution prepared and injected to check interference at R.T. of Brivaracetam.

Results of Specificity.

Description	Observation
Blank	No interference at R.T. of Brivaracetam due to blank
Placebo	No interference at R.T. of Brivaracetam due to placebo

Chromatograms:

Fig. No. 17 Typical chromatogram of Blank solution.

Fig. No. 18 Typical chromatogram of Placebo solution.

Acceptance criteria:

Blank: There should be no Interference at R.T. of Brivaracetam.

Placebo: There should be no Interference at R.T. of Brivaracetam.

Data interpretation: Blank and placebo was not having interference at R.T. of Brivaracetam. Hence

developed chromatographic method passed the criteria for specificity.

4) Linearity and Range

Linearity of an analytical method is its ability to elicit test results that are proportional to the concentration of analyte in samples within a given range.

Linearity Data for Brivaracetam:

Level	Conc (µg/mL)	Area	Mean	% RSD
50%	10.00	3685230	3685606	0.105
		3681956		
		3689633		
75%	15.00	5530302	5528923	0.031
		5527005		
		5529463		
100%	20.00	7453690	7456764	0.040
		7459630		
		7456972		
125%	25.00	9287610	9281729	0.063
		9275903		
		9281675		
150%	30.00	11216920	11218046	0.074
		11226894		
		11210325		

Fig. No. 19 Calibration curve of Brivaracetam

Data of linearity of Brivaracetam:

Sr no.	Parameter	Result value	Acceptance criteria
1	Beer's linearity range	10.0 - 30.0 µg/mL	NA
2	Correlation coefficient (R ²)	0.99996	NLT 0.98
3	Intercept	-92860.80	To be report
4	Slope	376353.72	To be report
5	% RSD for area at each level	NA	NMT 2.0

The respective linear equation for Brivaracetam was:

$$Y = M X + C$$

$$Y = 376353.72 X + -92860.80$$

Where, X = concentration of Analyte in µg/mL

Y = is area of peak.

M = Slope

C= Intercept

Chromatograms:

Fig. No. 20 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 50%.

Fig. No. 21 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 75%.

Fig. No. 22 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 100%.

Fig. No. 23 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 125%.

Fig. No. 24 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 150%.

CONCLUSION:

From the calibration curve it was concluded that the Brivaracetam shows linear response in the range of 10.0 - 30.0 µg /ml. The Regression value was found well within the limit.

5) Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ):

σ = 26785.61 (Residual standard deviation of a regression line)
 s = 376353.72 (Slope)

Detection limit (LOD):

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \sigma / S$$

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times 26785.61 / 376353.72$$

$$\text{LOD} = 0.235 \mu\text{g/mL}$$

Quantitation limit (LOQ):

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma / S$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times 26785.61 / 376353.72$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 0.712 \mu\text{g/mL}$$

6) ACCURACY (RECOVERY):

The accuracy of an analytical method is the closeness of test results obtained by that method to the true value. The accuracy of an analytical method is determined by applying the method to analyzed samples to which known amounts of analyte have been added.

Result and statistical data of Accuracy of Brivaracetam

Level (%)	Area	Recovered conc (µg/mL)	Added conc (µg/mL)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery	% RSD
50	3775426	10.13	10.16	99.70	99.80	0.56
	3700452	9.93	10.00	99.30		
	3771098	10.12	10.08	100.40		
100	7486027	20.09	20.08	100.05	99.37	0.63
	7450916	20.00	20.24	98.81		
	7455280	20.01	20.16	99.26		
150	11254709	30.20	30.08	100.40	100.26	0.99
	11307233	30.35	30.00	101.17		
	11120514	29.84	30.08	99.20		

Overall Recovery: 99.81 %

Chromatograms:

% RSD for Overall Recovery: 0.756

Fig. No. 25 Typical chromatogram of Accuracy 50%.

Fig. No. 26 Typical chromatogram of Accuracy 100%.

Fig. No. 27 Typical chromatogram of Accuracy 150%.

Acceptance criteria:

% Recovery for each level and overall recovery: 98.0 to 102.0%

% RSD for each level and overall recovery: NMT 2.0

Data interpretation: Recovery of analytical procedure was found well within acceptance criteria at all 3 levels. % Recovery not get hampered by changed in analyte concentration.

7) PRECISION

Precision of an analytical method is the degree of agreement among individual test results when the procedure is applied repeatedly to multiple samplings of a homogenous sample. Precision of an analytical method is usually expressed as standard deviation or relative standard deviation. Precision was performed on Test sample.

Result of Intra- day and Inter- Day Precision for Brivaracetam test sample assay:

	Sample	Test Sample (mg)	Area	% Assay
Repeatability	Sample 1	132.6	7412085	99.16
	Sample 2	133.2	7555410	100.62
	Sample 3	132.2	7315671	98.17
	Sample 4	132.8	7431693	99.27
	Sample 5	132.6	7305204	97.73
	Sample 6	132.1	7461303	100.20
	Mean			99.19
	STD DEV			1.1175
	% RSD			1.127
Intermediate precision (Inter-Day)	Sample 1	132.6	7335128	98.13
	Sample 2	132.7	7435879	99.40
	Sample 3	132.9	7326841	97.80
	Sample 4	133.2	7420028	98.82
	Sample 5	132.4	7443647	99.73
	Sample 6	132.7	7420819	99.20
	Mean			98.85
	STD DEV			0.751
	% RSD			0.760
Repeatability Plus Inter-day	Mean			99.019
	STD DEV			0.9255
	% RSD			0.935

Chromatograms:**Fig. No. 28 Typical chromatogram of Repeatability precision (Sample 1).**

Fig. No. 29 Typical chromatogram of Inter-day precision (Sample 1).

Acceptance criteria:

% Assay: % Assay value for each sample (Individual sample) and mean assay value for precision (6 sample), mean assay value intermediate precision (6 sample), and mean assay value for precision plus intermediate precision sample (12 samples): 90-110%

% RSD: % RSD for precision study samples (6 sample), Intermediate precision study samples (6 samples) and precision plus intermediate precision sample (12 samples): NMT 2.0

Data interpretation: % Assay and % RSD was found well within acceptance limit and hence method is precise (Reproducible).

8) ROBUSTNESS:

The robustness of an analytical method is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage.

Following changes made under Robustness:

- Change in Wavelength
- Change in flow rate
- Change in column oven temperature

Result of Robustness study:

Change in Parameter	R.T.	Standard area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates
Wavelength by +3 NM (213 NM)	3.16	7165025	1.37	9125
Wavelength by -3 NM (207 NM)	3.15	7305025	1.33	8573
Flow rate by +10% (1.1mL/min)	2.85	6769203	1.32	8463
Flow rate by -10% (0.9mL/min)	3.51	8103047	1.37	9210
Column oven temp by +2°C (37 °C)	3.14	7402536	1.37	9012
Column oven temp by -2°C (33 °C)	3.13	7468294	1.36	8916

Chromatograms:

A. Change in Wavelength by +3 NM:

Fig. No. 30 Typical chromatogram of Standard +3 NM.

B. Change in Wavelength by -3 NM:

Fig. No. 31 Typical chromatogram of Standard -3 NM.

C. Change in Flow rate by + 10% (1.1 mL/min)

Fig. No. 32 Typical chromatogram of Standard +10 F.R.%.

D. Change in Flow rate by - 10% (0.9 mL/min)**Fig. No. 35 Typical chromatogram of Standard -2°C C.O.T.**

Acceptance criteria:

Chromatography (System suitability) acceptance criteria should not get failed.

Data interpretation: From the above results, it was concluded that the system suitability test result was found well within the limits and analytical method was robust.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

• The present work involved the development of simple, accurate, precise and suitable RP-HPLC method. • Literature survey revealed that several methods have been reported for determination of XXX in bulk drug or in pharmaceutical dosage forms. Hence, in the present study, a new, sensitive and suitable reversed-phase high performance liquid chromatography method was developed and validated for the determination of XXX in bulk drug and pharmaceutical dosage form. • In developed RP-HPLC method, the analyte were resolved by using isocratic program and mobile phase was used Methanol : Water (75:25 % v/v) at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min, on HPLC system containing UV- visible detector with Openlab EZ-Chrome Software and Kromasil C18, 250 mm X 4.6 mm, 5 μ m. The detection was carried out at 258 nm. • The results of analysis in the developed method were validated in terms of linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, limit of detection and limit of quantification. • The developed method has several advantages, including reproducibility of results, rapid analysis, simple sample preparation and improved selectivity as well as sensitivity. The regression coefficient (r^2) for each analyte is not less than 0.999 which shows good linearity. The % recovery was in the acceptable range in tablet dosage form. The %RSD was also less than 2% showing high degree of precision of the proposed method.

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